

ELECTROSTATICS, ITS ESTABLISHMENT AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH
OTHER FIELDS.

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Mirzayeva Khadichahon Musajon qizi

Fergana State University

Student of the group 20.13 of the Faculty of Physics and Technology

Toshpo'latova Zilolaxon

Fergana State University

Student of the group 20.13, Faculty of Physics and Technology

Topivoldiyev Jasurbek

Fergana State University

Faculty of Physics and Technology 20.13 "A" - group student

Anatation: *This article discusses electrostatics, its history and other fields, and its application in life.*

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One of the main issues in teaching the electrical department is to further expand their knowledge of electrical charges, their effects and related events, to raise their initial understanding of the department to the level of scientific understanding.

Electrostatics is the branch of physics that studies the field of static electric charges and their interactions. The electric field created by static electric charges is called the electrostatic field.

It is known that atoms consist of a positively charged nucleus and electrons orbiting around the nucleus in closed orbits. In uncharged atoms, the sum of the negative charges of the electrons is equal to the positive charge of the nucleus. Such bodies are called electroneutral bodies. If the electroneutrality is disturbed as a result of such an impact, such an object will be charged. When the negative charges in a body are greater than the positive charges, the body is negatively charged, and when it is low, the body is positively charged.

$$q = \pm Ne$$

The charges of an electron and a proton are equal in magnitude, and their signs are opposite.

Therefore, the electric charge of an electron (or proton) can be called an elementary charge.

American scientist R. Miliken and Russian scientist AF Loffe experimented that an electron is negatively charged and its charge is $e = -1.6 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ C}$, and its mass is $m = 9.11$

* $1.67 \cdot 10^{-27}$ kg. proved. It was later proved that the charge of a proton is also quantitatively equal to the charge of an electron, but has a positive sign $e = 1.6 \cdot 10^{-19}$ C and a mass $m = 1.67 \cdot 10^{-27}$ kg.

The interaction between the charges takes place through an electric field. Any charge creates an electric field in the space around it.

Such an area can be determined by placing another positive charge on it. This positive charge is commonly called a "test" charge.

Depending on the level of force exerted by the field on the "test" charge, the intensity of this field is considered.

As a result of generalization of experimental conclusions, M. Faraday discovered the fundamental law of nature - the law of conservation of charge. According to him, the algebraic sum of electric charges does not change in an isolated system.

It has been proven that the values of charges do not change when measured in different inertial reference frames. So we conclude that an electric charge is a relativistic invariant, that is, the amount of charge does not depend on its velocity. But always two elementary charges with opposite signs are lost or formed.

Coulomb's law: The basic law of electrostatics is the law of interaction between two charged stationary point bodies.

The concept of a point electric charge is similar to that of a material point in mechanics, that is, its size can be ignored rather than the distance between the charges, and it does not change the area at that point.

The force of interaction of a two-point electric charge in a vacuum is directly proportional to the product of the magnitudes of each charged charge and inversely proportional to the square of the distance between the charges.

M. Faraday proposed to describe the electrostatic field using power lines.

Voltage lines (lines of force) are lines that correspond to the direction of the voltage vector at that point in the field applied to any point.

The value of the voltage is equal to the number of power lines passing through the unit surface perpendicular to the power lines at that point.

The voltage lines have a clear direction with each other.

The basic equations of electrostatics are a special case of Maxwell's equations. When electric charges are motionless, that is, when there is no electric current, there is no magnetic field, and the electric field remains constant. The phenomenon of the formation of electric charges on the surface of non-electrified bodies under the influence of an external electrostatic field is called electrical induction or electrostatic induction.

Electricity (electrostatics) is a set of phenomena related to the presence, movement and effect of electric charges. In the 8th century BC, the Greek philosopher F. Miletus noted that a piece of ebonite rubbed on a woolen cloth would attract fluff and other light objects. Some time later, in 1600, the English physician William Gilbert discovered that silk-coated glass and a number of other substances had similar properties. used the term Objects that attract light objects as a result of friction are called electrically charged or

electrically charged bodies. It was not until the 18th century that electrical phenomena were studied rapidly.

The development of the doctrine of electricity can be divided into 3 stages:

1 the collection of experimental evidence and the basic concepts, the period of defining the laws (8th century BC, mid-19th century);

2.the period of formation of the doctrine of the electromagnetic field (second half of the 19th century);

3. The period of formation of the electric atomistic theory (late 19th century to early 20th century).

The English physicist S. Gray discovered the electrical conductivity of individual bodies and determined that all bodies in nature are divided into conductors and insulators (1727).

French physicist Sh. Dufay and American scientist B. Franklin found that there are 2 types of electric charges. The formation of charges in ebonite is considered negative, and the formation of glass is considered a positive sign. Scientists have determined the interaction of these charges (the repulsion of charges of the same sign, the attraction of charges of different signs) (1747-53).

The English physicist and chemist G. Cavendish (1773) and the French physicist Sh. Coulomb (1785) discovered the law of charge interaction.

In the mid-18th century, the study of the biological and physiological effects of electricity in the atmosphere, electric sparks, and electric discharges developed.

The discovery of the Leiden jar by the German scientist EG Kleist and the Dutch physicist P. Muschen Brook (1745-46). It paved the way for the study of electrical phenomena and their physiological effects.

B. Franklin, Russian scientists M. Lomonosov and G. Richman proved the electrical nature of lightning, developed his theory of electricity (1750-53).

Academician F. U. Epinus, dealing with the phenomenon of electrostatic induction and non-uniform distribution of charges on the surface of a conductor (1750), expressed his views on the law of conservation of electric charge.

Italian physicists L. Galvani (1786) and A. Volta (1792) studied experimental electrical phenomena and demonstrated the formation of alternating current after the discovery of chemical and contact sources of electricity. There were attempts.

Russian physicist V.V. Petrov invented the electric arc (1802), which showed that electricity could be used for lighting and smelting metals in furnaces.

A. Volta discovered the law of separation of contact potentials (1795).

The German physicist G. Ohm found experimentally that the current depends on the length of the conductor, the cross section and the number of galvanic elements (1820).

The English physicist J. Joule (1841) and the Russian physicist E. H. Lance (1842) discovered a law (see Joule-Lens law) that determines the amount of heat released from a conductor when an unknowing current passes through it.

The Danish physicist H. Ersted discovered the effect of an electric current on a magnetic shaft (1820) and began a new stage in the theory of electricity, the study of the magnetic properties of current.

The French physicist, mathematician and chemist A. Ampere studied the interaction of constant currents and determined that the forces of interaction of two elementary currents are directly proportional to the product of currents (1820) (Ampere's law).

French physicists J. Bio, F. Savar and P. Laplace discovered the law that determines the intensity of the magnetic field generated by a current (1820).

Thus, it has been proved that both permanent magnets and electric currents can be sources of magnetic fields. put forward the hypothesis.

At the beginning of the 20th century, discoveries about the structure of the atom revealed that molecular currents were formed due to the rotational motion of the electrons in the atoms around the nucleus.

After the great work of H. Ersted and A. Ampère, magnetism became an integral part of the theory of electricity.

By this time, the scientific activity of the English physicist M. Faraday began. In particular, his 2 discoveries: the phenomenon of electromagnetic induction (1831) and the laws of electrolysis (1834) are important in the history of physics. With these discoveries, Faraday laid the theoretical foundations for the many technical applications of electricity.

E. H. Lens defined the general rule for determining the direction of induced electric current (1833) (Lens rule).

M. Faraday introduced the concepts of electric and magnetic fields in his work, showed that the properties of this material environment play a key role in the change of the field and its distribution in the environment.

M. Faraday's laws of electrolysis made an important contribution to the development of electrochemistry and laid the foundation for the theory that electric charges are discrete.

The second period of the doctrine of electricity is associated with the discoveries of the second half of the 19th century. Faraday's theory of electric and magnetic fields was deepened and developed by the English physicist J. K. Maxwell. Maxwell's greatest scientific achievement was the development of the theory of the electromagnetic field (1860-65). He expresses this theory in the form of a system of several equations describing the basic laws of electromagnetic phenomena (see Maxwell's equations). Maxwell based his theory that the change of electric field over time creates a rotating magnetic field and, conversely, the change of magnetic field over time creates a rotating electric field.

Maxwell's prediction of the existence of electromagnetic waves and their propagation in space at the speed of light (1865) led him to say that light also consists of electromagnetic waves (1865).

The German physicist G. Gers played an important role in the implementation of this theory in the experiments of electromagnetic waves. Russian physicist AS Popov used electromagnetic waves to invent radio.

M.K. According to Maxwell's theory, electromagnetic waves have energy and exert pressure on the body.

The motion of the energy of electromagnetic waves in closed media and the law of its conservation were first described in general by the Russian physicist N. A. Umov (1874).

The pressure of electromagnetic waves, including light, was proved experimentally by the Russian physicist P. N. Lebedev (1899).

By the end of the 19th century, a new third period of development of electric distribution, based on Maxwell's theory, the kinetic theory of matter, and others, had begun. The doctrine of the discreteness of the electrical structure (atomistic structure) began to emerge.

The theory of electrons, the theory of the structure of matter based on the idea that there are electrified particles in the atom, developed. The services of the French physicist J. A. Poincaré, the Dutch physicist H. A. Lorentz, and the English physicist J. J. Thomson played an important role in this.

The Irish physicist G. Helmholtz, based on Faraday's laws of electrolysis, proposed the discreteness of the electric charge, the existence of the smallest electric charge - the elementary charge (1881).

The English physicist J.J. Stoney called this elementary charge "electron" (1891). The study of new phenomena, such as cathode rays, thermoelectric emissions, photoelectric phenomena, and radioactivity, has shown that atoms actually contain electrons.

E. Rutherford proposed a planetary model of atomic structure. By this time, the electronic theory of the structure of matter had faced a number of challenges.

The doctrine of electricity is the basis of electrical engineering, radio engineering, electronics, automation, television and many other industries.

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